

Measurement and Simulation of the Axial Neutron Flux Profile in a HALEU TRISO Critical Experiment using the ^{197}Au Radiative Capture Reaction

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ABSTRACT

TRI-structural ISOtropic (TRISO) fuel forms are gaining interest and attention for use in new and existing advanced reactor designs globally. Additionally, small modular reactors and micro-reactors concepts are exploring the use of high-assay low-enriched uranium (HALEU) fuel with $\leq 20\%$ ^{235}U enrichment. The TRISO-form HALEU-fueled Experiment for Transport Applications (THETA) experiment was recently performed at the National Criticality Experiments Research Center (NCERC) in collaboration with Kairos Power to explore HALEU TRISO transportation validation cases through the Department of Energy's and Nuclear Regulatory Commission's Collaboration for Criticality Safety Support for Commercial-Scale HALEU for Fuel Cycles and Transportation (DNCSH). As an addition to the full diagnostic suite, a gold wire was placed axially in the voided central heater portion of a critical configuration operated at sufficient power level to activate the gold wire to measure the axial neutron flux profile. The configuration selected contained hollow stainless steel rods on the outer periphery of the fuel-containing graphite monolithic core. This work examines the measurement and analysis of the gold wire post-irradiation to construct a relative axial neutron flux profile and investigates comparisons to MCNP simulation.

Keywords: Reactor Physics, Criticality Experiment, HALEU, TRISO, Flux Profile

1. INTRODUCTION

TRI-structural ISO-topic (TRISO) fuel was originally developed for high-temperature reactors, constructed with layers of graphite buffer, silicon carbide, and pyrolytic carbon surrounding the fuel kernel in the middle as shown in Figure 1. Frequently, this fuel kernel is a uranium oxycarbide (UCO) or uranium nitride (UN) with a uranium enrichment in the 5- to 19.75-wt.% range, which is considered High-Assay Low Enriched Uranium (HALEU). As more advanced reactor designs consider the use of HALEU TRISO fuel, there has been a shift in regulatory focus towards validation of safe, demonstrably sub-critical transportation methods for this fuel, especially at commercial-scales. The most direct method of criticality safety validation is to compare the application with a benchmark experiment that has many of the same characteristics, such as fuel type, fission spectrum, etc. Unfortunately, there are currently no benchmarks available that closely match the conditions for the transportation of HALEU TRISO. [1]

TRISO-form HALEU-fueled Experiment for Transport Applications (THETA) was a critical experiment campaign designed to resemble a transportation container for TRISO fuel under normal and accident-like scenarios. This was completed through the use of three interstitial materials in a total of six different configurations. Thin-walled stainless steel tubes were added to represent the transport container, polyethylene rods were used to simulate water ingress, and borated polyethylene rods were added to quantify the effects of adding additional boron neutron absorber to act as an additional safety measure in the design of the transportation container. This experimental campaign was executed at the National

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Criticality Experiments Research Center (NCERC) in February 2025, on the Comet critical assembly using the Deimos experimental testbed. [2, 3] THETA was funded by the DOE/NRC Collaboration for Criticality Safety Support for Commercial-Scale HALEU for Fuel Cycles and Transportation (DNCSH) [4] and was a partnership between Los Alamos National Laboratory and Kairos Power, LLC.

Figure 1. Illustration of a CNPS fuel compact and TRISO fuel kernel.

Foil samples can be included in critical experiments at NCERC to provide supplemental information on nuclear data: reaction rates and ratios, flux profiles, or with enough reactions, perform a complete neutron spectrum characterization. In recent years, only small foil samples on the order of 0.5 inch in diameter thicknesses around tens of thousands of an inch are used in critical experiment diagnostics at NCERC. Recent interest in complete axial measurements has re-established dialogue related to wire measurements and has solicited interest in obtaining a wire spool sample measurement rig for non-destructive assay of wire. Given the unique geometry of this particular experiment, a desire was raised to obtain an axial flux profile and re-establish flux wire measurements, even if destructive analysis was required. This experiment marks a re-establishment of axial activation wire measurements at NCERC.

1.1. The NCERC Counting Laboratory (NCERC-CL)

The NCERC Counting Laboratory (NCERC-CL) is a reactor dosimetry and radiation metrology capability at NCERC. The NCERC-CL supports NCERC critical experiment diagnostics as a home base for activation and fission foil measurements and reactor kinetics measurements. NCERC-CL maintains a wide array of activation and fission foils spanning the IRDFF-II reaction library and includes noteworthy materials and equipment: highly-enriched uranium, depleted uranium, neptunium, and plutonium samples, multiple high-purity germanium detectors (HPGes) in a variety of shielding configurations and an automated 16-slot sample changer. More information on recent NCERC-CL research and capabilities for supporting critical experiments at NCERC can be found in further relevant publications [5, 6, 7, 8].

2. EXPERIMENT DESCRIPTION

The TRISO fuel used in this experiment, shown in Figure 2a, was originally used as part of the Compact Nuclear Power Source (CNPS) experiments performed at the Los Alamos Critical Experiments Facility (LACEF) at Los Alamos National Laboratory between 1987 and 1991 on the Mars vertical lift machine [9]. This fuel is now being used at NCERC on the Deimos experiment platform on the Comet critical assembly machine. Experiments focus on validating criticality safety and reactor physics calculations of HALEU systems. Each 0.87 mm diameter TRISO particle itself contains a UCO kernel with uranium content enriched to around 19.9% by weight. The UCO kernel is then surrounded by a carbon buffer and concentric shells of pyrolytic carbon and silicon carbide. Stacks of these fuel compacts were assembled into fuel rods 95 cm in height. The core of THETA consisted of an inner reflector region with a hexagonally pitched array and an outer reflector region with a square pitched array as illustrated in Figure 2b. The inner array is inserted or withdrawn to control reactivity by remote operation of the Comet assembly.

The core is reflected on four sides by 16.8 cm thick beryllium metal to decrease neutron leakage. The top and bottom of the core is axially reflected by additional graphite. The core configuration detailed in Table I and used for this work, is the original Deimos configuration.

(a) Singular HALEU TRISO fuel compact enriched to 19.9% ^{235}U .

(b) Partially defueled core of THETA with top axial graphite reflector removed.

Figure 2. The inner hexagonal-pitch region is moved in and out of the outer stationary square pitch region to control reactivity. Radial beryllium reflector is seen on the periphery of the square pitch region.

Table I. Nominal Specifications of the THETA Experiment and Fuel.

Core Specification	Value	Fuel Specification	Value
Fuel Rods	250 - 326	Rod Length	94 cm
Moderator	Graphite	Rod Diameter	1.27 cm
Reflector	Beryllium	Enrichment	19.9%
Reflector Thickness	16.8 cm	TRISO Packing Fraction	0.622
Square Pitch	3.55 cm	U Mass per Rod	127.8 g
Hexagonal Pitch	5.00 cm		

The cavities in the inner and outer graphite moderator blocks can be filled with fuel rods or interstitial materials of interest to adjust the system reactivity and spectrum. Three configurations of the THETA experiment were performed to simulate different transportation scenarios. All were instrumented with ex-core neutron detectors to perform neutron noise analysis, summarized in other work [10]. Configuration 1, detailed in Table II, was considered the baseline measurement.

Table II. Rod Loading and Excess Reactivity for THETA Configuration 1 (this work).

Configuration	Fuel Rods	HDPE Rods	Borated Rods	Excess Reactivity (ρ)
1	326	0	0	17.1

3. THEORY

In general, the goal of reactor dosimetry is to obtain neutron spectral information in the form of reaction rates or reaction rate ratios, ratios of spectral averaged cross sections, or spectral characterization.

A reaction rate is an integral quantity defined by the product of the energy dependent neutron flux and the specific energy dependent neutron reaction cross section. This quantity physically represents the number of atoms produced per second, and in this case is normalized to the number of parent atoms. A reaction rate can be modeled in neutron transport codes such as MCNP, Serpent, or OpenMC, us-

ing a neutron flux tally and a cross section multiplier. It is an extremely valuable quantity that can be used for simulation verification and validation in addition to parameters such as k_{eff} reported in criticality benchmarks. Gamma spectroscopy of neutron irradiated flux monitors, activation foils or wires, can provide values for comparison to simulation. The technique uses simple corrections derived from the solution to the neutron irradiation differential equation problem with corrections for measurement technique.

Given recent attention to HALEU TRISO, additional diagnostic measurements are an important additional reactor physics parameter of interest to provide additional model validation. Measurements such as those described in this work may be performed for comparison to simulations of new small modular reactor designs and demonstration reactors.

4. METHODS

4.1. Measurements

Prior to irradiation, experimenters placed and secured a pure gold wire approximately 1m in length and 0.0254 cm (0.010") in diameter into the empty central cavity of the Configuration 1 experiment as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Gold wire placed into the central void of the core and held in place above the top graphite reflector.

The experiment was brought supercritical and the fission power was increased until the desired power level was reached. The reactor power was then stabilized by finding delayed-critical and irradiating the sample wire for approximately one hour before shutting down the assembly. After about 30 minutes to allow for dose rates to subside and facilitate retrieval, the gold wire was retrieved and immediately transferred to the NCERC-CL for processing and subsequent gamma spectroscopy measurements.

Once at NCERC-CL, the gold wire was physically separated into approximately 10 cm long segments and then wound around a pair of forceps into a compact spiral. Each spiral wire segment was then placed into a sample planchet and placed on the furthest slot of the highly-shielded HPGe at approximately 20 cm offset from the detector face such that any coincidence summation or sum peaks were minimized. The samples were left in place inside of the shields until approximately 1×10^4 net counts, corresponding to roughly 1% counting uncertainty, were collected in the peak corresponding to ^{198}Au decay. This process was repeated until all samples had been assayed once. Each spectra was then analyzed with a custom Python script relying heavily on the `Becquere1` gamma spectroscopy library as illustrated in Figure 5 to determine end-of-irradiation count rates normalized to segment length [11].

The analysis methodology follows a similar but modified version to that described in ASTM E720 [12]

(a) Gold wire segments were wound around forceps to create uniform samples to fit in sample holders.

(b) HPGe and sample holder.

Figure 4. Sample preparation and HPGe measurement setup.

to obtain a *ratio* of absolute decay corrected specific activities. The main difference between this work and ASTM E720 is that the normalization to the target isotope mass is based on the assumption made that segment length is a proper surrogate for mass, assuming uniform wire thickness. The commonly shared terms, such as the detector efficiencies and corrections for decay during irradiation, cancel, leaving only the wire-segment specific corrections related to the detector dead-time correction, the decay times, and the correction for decay during measurement. In short, the end-of-irradiation ^{198}Au count rates normalized to the segment length were used to determine relative reaction rates. The relative re-

(a) Gamma peak near 412 keV from ^{198}Au decay.

(b) Peak fit with gaussian model and absolute residuals vs. channel.

Figure 5. Example of the counts vs. energy bin for the gold decay peak and the corresponding gaussian peak fit.

action rate values were then normalized to the mean of the measured dataset. The nominal values and uncertainty tabulated in the International Reactor Dosimetry and Fusion File II (IRDF-II) library, the international standard for reactor dosimetry applications [13] were used.

4.2. Simulation

A simplified MCNP model, as illustrated in Figure 6, was used for simulations. At the time of documenting this work, a fully explicit neutronic model of this experiment was in progress for submission to the International Criticality Safety Benchmark Evaluation Project (ICSBEP) handbook. The main differ-

ences between the simplified model used in this work and the detailed model are the explicit treatment of the TRISO particles in the fuel compacts. The well-documented differences in neutron transport when homogenization of fuel particles are performed is acknowledged by the authors and the impact may be investigated in future work. The $^{197}\text{Au}(n,\gamma)^{198}\text{Au}$ reaction rate was simulated in MCNP6.3 by introducing a mesh tally (FMESH) to the model in the central heater void region where the gold wire was located, as shown in Figure 6a and as demonstrated in Figure 3. The mesh was subdivided into 20

Figure 6. THETA experiment MCNP model cross sectional views with the inner core region fully inserted.

stacked cylindrical elements with no radial or azimuthal binning. The mesh tally multiplier utilized a dummy material comprised of pure ^{197}Au and a multiplicative factor of the energy dependent radiative capture cross section (MT 102). For these simulations, we examined the impact of the flux profile with and without the room, as well as with and without $S(\alpha, \beta)$ thermal scattering treatment for water bound in concrete and no significant impact was found on the results. The core and reflector effectively insulate the samples from room return in this case.

5. RESULTS

Figure 7a displays the simulated MCNP data with and without the surrounding room compared to the measured and analyzed data obtained by the gold wire measurements with accompanying tally zones in Figure 7b. MCNP data shown with $1\text{-}\sigma$ Monte Carlo uncertainties. Measured data shown with propagated counting and nuclear data uncertainties. Overall there is significant agreement between the measured data and simulated data. Near the top of the core, however, there is less agreement with simulation. These deviations may be due to differences in the MCNP model and the as-built experiment near the top part of the reflector, but more simulations with the as-built benchmark model in the future can assist in answering this hypothesis by comparing updated flux profile results. It is also possible that the physical placement of the wire during measurement did not match the modeled position. A more elegant wire placement method is being developed based on lessons-learned for deployment in future irradiations.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Overall, good agreement between simulation and measurement was observed. Potential changes have been noted to improve future measurements. The use of multiple wires can provide not only axial reaction rates, but reaction rate ratios. Ratios can be used to validate specific energy regions of the neutron flux profile. An investment in an automated wire spooler would make these types of axial measure-

(a) $^{197}\text{Au}(n, \gamma)^{198}\text{Au}$ reaction rate profile relative to the mean.

(b) MCNP model with mesh grid shown in central cavity to generate data points in Fig. 7a.

Figure 7. Measured and simulated results as a function of distance from bottom of the fueled core region (shown as the yellow-and green interface in Fig. 7b) with illustrated data point generation locations.

ments more streamlined to perform without the need to destructively analyze longer wire samples. Many upcoming experiments will benefit from activation wire measurements. Additionally, improvements can be made to the experiment design to have more confidence in the exact positioning of the wire, which was a possible explanation for deviations from simulation.

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REFERENCES

- [1] L. Fassino, M. N. Dupont, I. Al-Qasir, W. A. Wieselquist, and W. Marshall. "Current State of Benchmark Applicability for Commercial-Scale HALEU Fuel Transport." Technical Report ORNL/TM-2024/3248, Oak Ridge National Laboratory (2024).
- [2] H. R. Trellue, T. E. Cutler, E. P. Luther, N. A. Wynne, J. L. Lee, J. N. Downey, S. W. Stinson, K. N. Stolte, R. G. Sanchez, A. Maldonado, and H. P. Morbach. "Design of a High Assay Low-Enriched Uranium (HALEU) TRI-structural ISOtropic (TRISO) Critical Experiment for Advanced Reactor Validation." Technical Report LA-UR-25-20169, Los Alamos National Laboratory (2025).
- [3] K. N. Stolte, T. E. Cutler, A. Maldonado, H. R. Trellue, J. N. Downey, N. A. Wynne, S. W. Stinson, and R. G. Sanchez. "Deimos: HALEU TRISO Heated Critical Experiment Data." Technical Report LA-UR-25-22793, Los Alamos National Laboratory (2025).
- [4] W. Wieselquist. "DOE/NRC Criticality Safety for Commercial-Scale HALEU for Fuel Cycle and Transportation (DNCSH) Project Charter." Technical report, Oak Ridge National Laboratory (2024).
- [5] N. Whitman, R. Weldon, M. Gooden, and J. Hutchinson. "Measured Reaction Rate Ratios of ^{235}U , ^{238}U , ^{237}Np , ^{239}Pu Samples in the PFUNS ^{235}U Prompt Fission Neutron Spectrum Criticality Experiment." *EPJ Web of Conferences* (In review).
- [6] R. Charrette, R. Weldon, N. Whitman, J. Hutchinson, and J. Mattingly. "Prompt Fission Uranium Neutron Spectrum (PFUNS) Spectrum Adjustment." [Unpublished manuscript].
- [7] J. Hutchinson, J. Alwin, T. Cutler, M. Gooden, N. Kleedtke, D. Neudecker, N. Thompson, R. Weldon, N. Whitman, and R. Little. "Reaction Rate Ratios for Recent Fast Metal Experiments with Large Plutonium Masses." *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, **volume 199**(1), pp. 42–60 (2025).
- [8] N. Whitman, B. Pierson, R. Weldon, T. Cutler, M. Gooden, J. Hutchinson, R. Sanchez, T. Grove, and J. Goda. "Godiva IV central cavity neutron environment characterization with threshold neutron detectors." *EPJ Web Conf*, **volume 308**, p. 06005 (2024). URL <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/202430806005>.
- [9] G. E. Hansen and R. G. Palmer. "Compact Nuclear Power Source Critical Experiments and Analysis." *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, **volume 103**(3), pp. 237–246 (1989). URL <https://doi.org/10.13182/NSE89-A23674>.
- [10] C. Kostelac, T. Cutler, N. Thompson, N. Whitman, C. Campbell, N. Satvat, and A. Alajo. "Reactor Kinetics Measurements of a HALEU TRISO-Fueled Critical Experiment." *Proceedings of PHYSOR 2026 (in review)* (2026).
- [11] M. Bandstra, A. Persaud, J. Curtis, C. Chow, D. Hellfeld, M. Salathe, and J. Vavrek. "becquerel (bq) v0.4.0." (2021). URL <https://github.com/lbl-anp/becquerel>.
- [12] ASTM International. *Standard Guide for Selection and Use of Neutron Sensors for Determining Neutron Spectra Employed in Radiation-Hardness Testing of Electronics*. ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA, e720-16 edition (2016). URL <https://www.astm.org/e0720-16.html>.
- [13] A. Trkov, P. Griffin, S. Simakov, L. Greenwood, K. Zolotarev, R. Capote, D. Aldama, V. Chechev, C. Destouches, A. Kahler, C. Konno, M. Košťál, M. Majerle, E. Malambu, M. Ohta, V. Pronyaev, V. Radulović, S. Sato, M. Schulc, E. Šimečková, I. Vavtar, J. Wagemans, M. White, and H. Yashima. "IRDF-II: A New Neutron Metrology Library." *Nuclear Data Sheets*, **volume 163**, pp. 1–108 (2020).